

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF SPIDER SILK

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SUMMARY: The mechanical properties of *Nephila clavipes* spider silk are presented to illustrate the unique combination of strength and toughness and the anisotropy of spider silk. The tensile properties of the silk of *Nephila clavipes* spider were characterized by simple elongation, transverse compression and torsion under various humidity conditions using an ultra-sensitive testing system. It was founded that, although the properties of the spider silks vary from species to species, they all have a high level of combined strength and toughness as well as shear resistance much greater than that of some of the toughest synthetic fibers such as the aramid fibers.

KEYWORDS: spider silk, tensile modulus, compressive modulus, shear modulus, micromasurement instrument, anisotropic properties, combined strength and toughness

INTRODUCTION

Strength and toughness are usually considered mutually exclusive properties for materials. In spite of the progress made over the past century in polymeric fiber science and technologies, the search for a truly strong and tough fiber continues. It is of practical and scientific interest to explore the limit of strength and toughness of fibrous materials; and to examine the factors which contribute to the development of a combination of strength and toughness in materials. The answers to these questions may be found in nature.

In the world of natural fibers, spider silk has long been recognized as the wonder fiber for its unique combination of high strength and rupture elongation. An earlier study, as shown in Figure 1, indicated spider silk has strength as high as 1.75 GPa at a breaking elongation of over 26% [1]. With toughness more than three times that of aramid and industrial fibers, spider silk continues to attract the attention of fiber scientists and hobbyists alike.

Considering the remarkable mechano-chemical properties of spider silk and fueled by the recent progress in biotechnology, there is a revival of interest in using spider silk as a model for the engineering of high energy absorption fibers [2]. Because of the fineness of spider silk, on the order of 4 μ m, the characterization of the mechanical properties of spider silks are limited to tensile mode. Little is known about the response of spider silks to other modes of deformation in the transverse direction and in torsion. It is the objective of this paper to present, for the first time, the tensile, transverse compression and torsional stress-strain properties of the spider silk from *Nephila Clavipes* spiders. This was made possible by using

an ultra sensitive micromasurement fiber testing system developed by Kawabata [3]. From these experimental data, the engineering properties: tensile modulus, transverse compressive modulus, and shear modulus of the spider silk was determined.

Figure 1: Tensile stress-strain behavior of *agiope aurentia* spider silk

SPIDER SILK AND SPECIMEN PREPARATION

There are over one million species of spiders on earth. Less than one percent of the spiders are orb weavers or silk makers. Properties of spider silks vary by species and by functions. Depending upon the species an individual spider has more than five different silk glands where silks of different properties are produced before extrusion through three pairs of spinnerets. The drag line originates in the ampullate gland and is extruded through the anterior spinnerets. Spider drag line is the strongest and toughest of the silks a spider makes. Spider drag line is the structural framework of a spider web and the life line of a spider. Chemically spider silk is a fibroin composed of twenty-odd alpha amino acids connected by the amide linkage (-COHN-). Alanine, serine and proline account for eighty percent of the amino acids. Drag lines of *Nephila Clavipes* (golden silk spider) and *Argiope Aurentia* (black and yellow spider) are among the strongest spider silks that we know. The strength of the drag line of *Nephila Clavipes* obtained by forcible silking was reported to be about 8 grams/denier and the strength of the drag line of *Argiope Aurentia* was over 12 grams/denier. In fact the strength and toughness of the silk from *Nephila Clavipes* was recognized for a long time by the South Sea Islanders who use the silk to make various kinds of bags and fish nets.

The spider silks used in this study were forcible spun from *Nephila Clavipes* spiders. They were provided by the US Army Natick R&DEC. The diameter of the silk, averaging over 117 measurements using the scanning electron microscope, is $3.67 \pm 0.47 \mu\text{m}$. Figure 2 shows a SEM picture of the silk. To facilitate handling of this delicate silk fiber, each fiber was mounted carefully on a cardboard frame with an opening equal to the gage length of the specimen. Thirty eight (38) samples were prepared for tensile test. Fifty (50) samples were prepared for transverse compression test whereas a total of twenty nine (29) samples were

prepared for torsion test. In order to investigate the effect of water on the mechanical properties of the spider silk half of each group of fibers were tested in ambient condition (20°C, 65% RH) and the other half of the specimen were tested in wet condition. The diameter of each fiber was measured and recorded prior to testing. All the tests were performed with the micromasurement system developed by Kawabata, including a micro tensile tester, torsion tester, and single fiber transverse compression tester 3.

Figure 2: SEM picture of spider silk

TENSILE PROPERTIES

The tensile properties of the spider silk were measured with the Kawabata micro tensile tester equipped with a special function "floating control". In order to minimize mechanical noise from the tester, a DC servo-motor system and simple transmission mechanism were used. The motor driving power is transmitted to the driving shaft through a helical rack-and-pinion mechanism similar to the driving mechanism of a microscope body tube. As shown in Figure 3, the control stroke of the driving chuck is 30 cm; however, in most of the fiber tensile testing, the dynamic stroke is measured in millimeters, requiring very precise measurement. Accordingly, the servo control system can be switched from the large stroke to the more precise small stroke zone at any portion of the large stroke travel. The control accuracy in the small stroke zone is 10 times more accurate, enabling a smoother control of fiber strain in the "floating zone". The maximum load capacity of this tester is 20 Kg and the maximum testing speed is 10 cm/sec. The position of the driving chuck can be controlled by an external servo-command signal (such as a sinusoidal signal) at any stage of the tensile testing process.

Figure 3: Floating-control tensile tester

The tensile testing were carried out under ambient and wet conditions with a cross head speed of 0.3 cm/min and a gage length of 2.53 cm. As shown in Figure 4, the stress-strain response of the spider silk tested under ambient condition assumed a sigmoidal shape with an initial modulus of 12.7 GPa. The breaking strength and elongation are 0.85 GPa and 20% respectively. When tested in water, there is no significant change in ultimate strength, however, a reduction of the initial modulus to 0.54 GPa and increased in ultimate elongation to 36% was observed. This phenomenon may be attributed to the rupturing of the secondary bonds which hold the helical molecular chains together resulting in greater elongation due to the uncoiling of the molecular chain.

Figure 4: Tensile stress-strain properties of spider silk

TRANSVERSE PROPERTIES

The compression tests in the transverse fiber diameter direction were carried out by placing a single fiber between a flat and mirror-finished steel plate and a mirror finished 0.2 mm square

compression plane. Because of the fineness of the spider fiber, a combination of sensitive instrumentation and mechanistic analysis are required in order to assure accurate measurement of the compressive stress-stain properties. For a compression force F , deforming the fiber cross-section as shown in Figure 5, its corresponding diameter change, U , can be calculated based on the following equations:

$$U = \frac{4F}{\pi} (S_{11} - \nu_{13}^2 S_{33}) \left(0.19 + \sin h^{-1} \frac{R}{b} \right) \quad (1)$$

where

$$B^2 = \frac{4F}{\pi} (S_{11} - \nu_{13}^2 S_{33}) \quad (2)$$

- R = fiber in undeformed state;
- $S_{11} = 1/E_T$
- $S_{22} = 1/E_L$
- E_T = transverse modulus
- E_L = longitudinal modulus
- F = compression force/unit length of fiber

For polymers with highly oriented molecular-chain such as spider silk it is approximated that $S_{33} \ll S_{11}$ and ν_{13} is small; therefore, Equation (1) may be reduced to

$$U = \frac{4F}{\pi} \frac{1}{E_T} \left(0.19 + \sin h^{-1} \frac{R}{b} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$B^2 = \frac{4F}{\pi E_T} \quad (4)$$

Figure 5: Diametrical compression of single fiber

The predictive accuracy of equation (3) have been verified using the Finite Element Method [3]. The FEM analysis also provides the stress distribution within the fiber cross-section. In the central area of the cross section, the maximum principal stress is:

$$\sigma_a = \frac{F}{2R} \quad (5)$$

and the maximum stress occurs in the area nearest the point of contact, approximated by

$$\sigma_m \approx 2\sigma_a \quad (6)$$

The compression force, F , is obtained by a moving electromagnetic coil acting against a strong fixed permanent magnet, which permits precise control of the compression rod.

The resolution of the displacement measurement is $0.05 \mu\text{m}$. The influence of the stiffness of the rod, etc. on the measured curve has been confirmed as negligible. Although U can be measured to a high degree of accuracy, the initial region of the F - U curve has some uncertainty, which causes a degree of uncertainty in the measurement of U values. In order to eliminate the effect of this uncertainty on E_T , the use of the slope of the F - U curve was applied as follows: From Equations 3 and 4, U is expressed only as a function of E_T for a fixed value F . For fixed F_1 and F_2 ,

$$U_1 = f(E_T)|_{F=F_1} \quad (7)$$

$$U_2 = f(E_T)|_{F=F_2} \quad (8)$$

where F_1 and F_2 are taken after passing the initial region to obtain the corresponding U_1 and U_2 , respectively, as well as the slope of the curve between F_1 and F_2 . The following relation may then be derived:

$$\Delta U = g(E_T) \quad (9)$$

or

$$E_T = g^{-1}(\Delta U) \quad (10)$$

where $\Delta U = U_2 - U_1$ and $g(E_T) = f(E_T)|_{F=F_2} - f(E_T)|_{F=F_1}$

The silk fibers were subjected to transverse cyclic loading at a compressive speed of $0.3 \mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$. under ambient and wet conditions, The compressive modulus of the fiber tested in ambient condition was 0.58 GPa . and the fiber experienced a high degree of permanent deformation ($\sim 20\%$). As shown in Figure 6. similar to the tensile behavior, a drastic reduction in compressive modulus was also observed when the test was performed under wet testing conditions.

Figure 6: Compressive stress-strain behavior of spider silk

TORSIONAL PROPERTIES

As shown in Figure 7, a single fiber having both ends reinforced by a paper backing using ceramic adhesives is hung on a top hook connected to a highly sensitive torque detector supported by two torque wires made of 0.2 mm piano wire. The bottom end is connected to a bar, and both ends of the bar are inserted into slits of a servo-driven cylindrical tube. The full scale of the torque meter is 0.0025 gf-cm/10 volt.

The specimens were tested in both ambient and wet conditions with a gage length of 1.33 mm at a torsion speed of 0.3π rad/sec. Because of the low level of torsional load, great care must be taken to contain the mechanical noise. Figure 8 shows the smoothed out torsional stress-strain curves illustrating the effect of moisture on the shear rigidity of the fibers. In both cases, a significant hysteresis was observed. A shear modulus of 3.58 GPa was determined for the silk tested in ambient condition. On the other hand, under wet condition, the silk fiber has low resistance to deform after overcoming the frictional moment. This appears to be consistent with the tensile deformation mechanism of the helical molecular structure.

Figure 7: Torsion tester for single fiber

Figure 8: Torsional stress-strain behavior of spider silk

CONCLUSIONS

Spider silk is an excellent model for the development of strong and tough materials. With a highly anisotropic mechanical behavior, the sensitivity of the initial modulus and elongation but not ultimate strength to moisture indicated an interesting molecular composite structure composed of well ordered fibrillar structures oriented in a primitive helical structure.

An ultra sensitive fiber testing system has been introduced and its capability demonstrated with the ultra-fine spider silk. This provides a useful tool in determining the engineering properties of single fibers as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Engineering properties of spider silk

Tensile Modulus: E_L (GPa)	Transverse Compressive Modulus: E_T (GPa)	Shear Modulus G (GPa)
12.71 (25.6%)*	0.579 (41.3%)*	3.58 (19.7%)*

* Coefficient of Variation

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